

Original Article

A timescale for the evolutionary history of sea spiders (Arthropoda: Pycnogonida)

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ABSTRACT

Sea spiders (Arthropoda: Pycnogonida) are an ancient lineage of chelicerates represented by a single living order, Pantopoda, and a patchy fossil record that provides limited information of their evolutionary timescale. The sudden appearance of Pantopoda in the Middle Jurassic has led several authors to propose a recent (Early Jurassic) origin and rapid diversification of modern pycnogonids. In contrast, a recent molecular clock study suggested Pantopoda originated before the Devonian, and diversified slowly, though the fossil calibrations on which it was based have since been revised. Here, we conduct timetree inference using a set of 13 mitochondrial protein-coding genes, 18S rRNA sequences, and 98 ultraconserved elements from 198 pycnogonid taxa, with calibrations reflecting the most recent interpretations of the sea spider fossil record. Our analyses estimate that pycnogonids diverged from other arthropods during the Cambrian (539–510 Mya), indicating about 100 Myr between Pycnogonida origin and pantopod diversification. The pycnogonid crown group (=Pantopoda) diversified during the Late Palaeozoic, in an interval spanning the early Silurian and the Late Devonian (435–367 Mya), preceding the appearance of the first pantopod fossil by ~206 Myr. Our analysis also implies that pantopod families originated between the Late Devonian and the Late Jurassic (378–154 Mya). This leads to very different estimates to previous studies based on the fossil record alone. However, previous molecular divergence time analyses yielded a similar evolutionary timescale, despite a notably different set of calibrations. This effective corroboration of previous evidence indicates that the underlying molecular evidence is informative and that the inferred long ghost lineages faithfully reflect the patchy nature of the pycnogonid fossil record which results from their low fossilization potential. Regardless, our results predict further fossil discoveries from different environments and periods, which might at least partially rewrite pycnogonid history.

Keywords: Bayesian phylogenetics; molecular timescale; Pycnogonida; Pantopoda; Chelicerata; phylogenomics; fossil record

INTRODUCTION

Sea spiders (Arthropoda, Pycnogonida) are exclusively marine chelicerates known from about 1400 extant species grouped into 11 families, all placed in the single order, Pantopoda. The phylogenetic relationships among these families remain widely debated (see [Sabroux *et al.* 2023a](#)). While most (if not all) Palaeozoic sea spider fossils show departures from the typical Pantopoda bauplan ([Bergström *et al.* 1980](#), [Sabroux *et al.* 2019](#), [Siveter *et al.* 2023](#)), Jurassic fossils were all assigned to Pantopoda

([Bamber 2007](#), [Charbonnier *et al.* 2007](#), [Sabroux *et al.* 2019](#)), in some cases to extant pantopod families. Based on the ‘sudden’ appearance of extant pycnogonid families after a long hiatus in the fossil record, and the continuous difficulties in resolving interfamilial pantopod relationships, it has been proposed that Pantopoda derived from a relict clade, and radiated recently (just before the middle Jurassic), after a drastic reduction of the total diversity of the sea spiders ([Arabi *et al.* 2010](#), [Sabroux *et al.* 2019](#), [2023b](#)). This hypothesis was tested for the first time in the study

of Ballesteros *et al.* (2021), which integrated a rich sampling of markers from various gene classes (ultraconserved elements, mitogenomes, nuclear ribosomal genes, and conserved exons). Ballesteros *et al.* (2021) used up to four sea spider fossils to calibrate their divergence time analysis, following the most up-to-date interpretations of their phylogenetic position at their time of writing (Siveter *et al.* 2004, Charbonnier *et al.* 2007, Wolfe *et al.* 2016). In that context, *Haliestes dasos* (Silurian) was used to define the minimum age of Pantopoda; *Palaeopycnogonides gracilis*, *Palaeoendeis elmii*, and *Collossopantopodus boissinensis* (Jurassic) were used, respectively, to define the minimal age of the Ammotheoidea, Phoxichilidioidea, and Colossendeoidea superfamilies (*sensu* Sabroux *et al.* 2023a). Based on their analyses Ballesteros *et al.* (2021) concluded that the pantopod crown-group was ancient (Cambrian to Silurian) and followed a ‘monotonic and near-constant process of diversification’, in contrast to previous interpretations. However, the anatomy and taxonomic status of pycnogonid fossils has recently been revised by Sabroux *et al.* (2023b, 2024) and Siveter *et al.* (2023). These authors concluded that *H. dasos* did not belong to crown-group Pantopoda and that *Palaeopycnogonides gracilis*, although clearly a pantopod, could not be assigned to any of the 11 extant families. In addition, these revisions provided for a more precise assignment of *C. boissinensis* as a calibration for the crown-group Colossendeidae. Here, we present a new time-scale for Pycnogonida that integrates recent reinterpretations of the pycnogonid fossil record, on a large dataset including 198 pycnogonid taxa distributed across 11 Pantopoda families. The dataset includes 13 mitochondrial protein-coding genes, 18S rRNA (18S) sequences, and 98 ultraconserved elements

(UCEs). Based on our molecular clock-dating analyses, we present a new evolutionary timescale for Pantopoda.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We assembled sequences currently available in the literature (Ballesteros *et al.* 2021, Sabroux *et al.* 2023a) and inferred a superalignment from which we estimated a new phylogeny. The inferred tree topology was fixed during timetree inference and calibrated using node age constraints informed by recent revisions of the anatomy and affinity of fossil sea spiders. Figure 1 illustrates occurrence data extracted from the Palaeobiology Database for Pycnogonida (access date: 9 September 2024), generated using a bespoke R script that used modified functions within the Palaeoverse R package (Jones *et al.* 2023), provided in our FigShare and GitHub repositories.

Supermatrix assembly

We assembled a molecular dataset composed of 13 mitochondrial protein-coding genes, 18S nuclear gene, and 98 UCEs retrieved from the sequences made available by Ballesteros *et al.* (2021) and Sabroux *et al.* (2023a). Our final dataset includes 198 pycnogonid taxa across the 11 families currently accepted in Pantopoda (Bamber *et al.* 2024). Outgroups include 13 non-pycnogonid chelicerates, four pancrustaceans, and three myriapods. Scorpions, non-Mesothelae spiders, and Trombidiformes mites were excluded from our analyses in order to prevent the potential emergence of tree reconstruction artefacts caused by convergent inversions of base composition bias in their mitochondrial genomes and long branch attraction (Hassanin *et al.*

The pycnogonid fossil record

Figure 1. Distribution of the sea spider fossil record through time.

Table 1. List of the fossil species used to derive the calibration densities used for timetree inference.

Node calibrated	Fossil species	Maximum age (Mya)	Minimum age (Mya)	Reference
Crown Euarthropoda	<i>Yicaris dianensis</i>	636.1	514	Wolfe <i>et al.</i> 2016
Crown Chelicerata	<i>Wisangocaris barbarahardyae</i>	538.8	509	Wolfe <i>et al.</i> 2016
Crown Colossendeidae	<i>Colossopantopodus boissinensis</i>	538.8	160.5	Sabroux <i>et al.</i> 2023b
Crown Phoxichilidioidea	<i>Palaeoendeis elmii</i>	538.8	160.5	Sabroux <i>et al.</i> 2023b
Crown Ascorhynchidae	? <i>Eurycyde golem</i>	538.8	149.2	Sabroux <i>et al.</i> 2019

Details about calibrated nodes: name of the fossil species used to calibrate the nodes, minimum and maximum ages, the study where the calibration was described. All calibrations used uniform densities with soft maxima and hard minima.

2005, Podsiadlowski *et al.* 2006, Arabi *et al.* 2012, Sabroux *et al.* 2023a). To further shield our study from long branch attraction artefacts, we followed Rota-Stabelli and Telford (2008) in not including Pseudoscorpiones or Mesostigmata in our dataset because these taxa yield long branches in mitogenomic trees. The list of included taxa and the accession numbers of the sequences used to build our alignment are given in the (Supporting Information Table S1).

Given that UCEs were only available for a subset of the species in our dataset, we decided to account for the potential impact that a high rate of missing data in UCEs (95.70% on average) could have on phylogeny and timetree inference. In order to do this, we built two alignments: one including UCEs ('Matrix 1', available in our FigShare repository) and another excluding them ('Matrix 2', available in our FigShare repository). To further reduce the possible impact of missing data on subsequent phylogenetic analyses, we included only those species for which mitochondrial genes and 18S sequences did not contain more than 70% of missing data; this rule was not applied to Austrodecidae (three specimens) or Rhynchothoracidae (one specimen) so that we could include these two rare families.

Alignments were inferred with MAFFT-linsi v.7.471 (Katoh and Standley 2013) and trimmed with trimAl v.1.2 (Gappyout option; Capella-Gutiérrez *et al.* 2009). The size of our 'Matrix 1' was reduced by ~38.4% (from 36 330 to 22 384 bp) and 'Matrix 2' by 62.4% (from 17 284 to 6505 bp). The first matrix includes mitochondrial (5579 bp), 18S (926 bp), and UCE (15 879 bp) nucleotide data, while 'Matrix 2' includes only the first two types of data.

Phylogenetic analyses

Phylogenetic analyses were conducted with IQTREE v.2.1.3 (Minh *et al.* 2020). We partitioned the superalignment, estimating model parameters for each gene independently, accounting for the varying rates of evolution of each gene in our dataset (-p). The partition scheme is available in our FigShare repository. ModelFinder (-m MFP) was used to select the best-fitting substitution models (Kalyaanamoorthy *et al.* 2017) and the ultrafast bootstrap approximation method to run 1000 bootstrap replicates (-B 1000) (Hoang *et al.* 2018).

Timetree inference analyses

Divergence-time estimation analyses were carried out with MCMCtree v.4.9h, a dating program that is part of the PAML package (Yang 2007). We fixed the tree topology inferred by IQTREE (see above), and used five fossil specimens to

calibrate the following nodes: Euarthropoda, Chelicerata, Colossendeidae, Phoxichilidioidea, and Ascorhynchidae. We used soft maxima and hard minima, and so the tail probabilities were 0.025 for the former and 1e-300 for the latter (i.e. lowest number that can be assigned without causing numerical issues). Justifications for the node age constraints used in this study can be found in Table 1, which follow best practice recommendations (Parham *et al.* 2012) and have already been described by Wolfe *et al.* (2016) and Sabroux *et al.* (2019, 2023b).

First, we analysed our full dataset (i.e. 'Matrix 1', mitochondrial, 18S, and UCEs) using all the five fossil constraints in Table 1 with MCMCtree under the approximate likelihood calculation (dos Reis and Yang 2011). Subsequently, we ran two sensitivity analyses. This was done to assess the impact of (1) including UCEs in the sequence alignment and (2) constraining node ages based on the Late Jurassic fossil ?*Eurycyde golem*. To achieve these goals we: (i) performed analyses including all five fossil constraints using 'Matrix 2' and (ii) performed analyses including only four fossil calibrations (?*E. golem* excluded) using 'Matrix 1'. The justification for the latter test stems from the fact that the status of ?*E. golem* as a member of the genus *Eurycyde* is still debated (Sabroux *et al.* 2019).

To assess whether calibration densities were in conflict with marginal densities (see dos Reis *et al.* 2015 for an exhaustive analysis of such potential truncation conflicts), we first ran MCMCtree without the data. Given that there were no issues identified, we then ran our analyses with our datasets under the geometric Brownian motion (GBM) (or autocorrelated-rates, Thorne *et al.* 1998, Yang and Rannala 2006) and the independent-rates log-normal (ILN, Rannala and Yang 2007, Lemey *et al.* 2010) relaxed-clock models to assess the effect of different clock models on divergence times. All our analyses were carried out under the HKY85+G4 nucleotide substitution model, where four categories were used to discretize the gamma distribution used to account for rate heterogeneity (Yang 1994). To specify a gamma distribution as a sensible rate prior, we first need an estimate of the mean evolutionary rate. Note that the mean of the gamma distribution (μ_T) will be equal to our rate estimate (\hat{r}), and thus equal to the shape parameter (α) divided into the scaling parameter (β); $\mu_T = \hat{r} = \alpha/\beta$. Given that we had already estimated our phylogeny (i.e. we had branch length estimates, and thus molecular distances) and established a constraint for the root age based on the fossil record [i.e. 5.7505 (time unit = 100 Myr), average between the minimum and maximum ages used to constrain the root age], we had everything we needed to estimate the mean evolutionary rate considering that molecular distances, d , are equal to the multiplication of rates, r ,

and times, t . Consequently, we divided the estimated tree height of our phylogenies (d) into the mean root age (t) to estimate the mean evolutionary rates of our phylogenies following $\hat{r} = d/t$. To account for the uncertainty in our rate estimates (i.e. $\sim 2.7\text{e-}10$ substitutions/site/year for the phylogeny inferred with ‘Matrix 1’ and $\sim 2.20\text{e-}10$ substitutions/site/year with ‘Matrix 2’), we specified a vague gamma rate prior with $\alpha = 2$. Therefore, the only parameter left to calculate to define our rate gamma prior was β (i.e. $\hat{r} = \alpha/\beta$; $\beta = \alpha/\hat{r}$). Our rate priors were therefore $\Gamma(2,7.2)$ when analysing ‘Matrix 1’ and $\Gamma(2,9.1)$ when analysing ‘Matrix 2’. Given the depth of this phylogeny, we can assume that the clock is severely violated (rate variance $\sigma^2 \approx 0.1$). We therefore specified a diffuse gamma prior on the rate variance: $\Gamma(1,10)$. We used a birth–death process with species sampling (Yang and Rannala 1997) with $\lambda = \mu = 1$ (equal per-lineage birth and death rates) and $\rho = 0.1$ (sampling fraction), parameter values that yield a uniform kernel density with which equal probabilities across all possible tree shapes are assumed. During the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling, we collected a total of 20 000 samples for each of the five independent chains that we ran for all analyses. We discarded the first 100 000 iterations as part of the burn-in phase and samples were collected every 1000 iterations (i.e. $100\,000 + 1000 \times 20\,000 = 20\,100\,000$ iterations per chain). MCMC diagnostics were carried out for every analysis and all the chains. The divergence times estimated when sampling from the prior and the posterior and for all datasets are reported in Supporting Information Table S5. We used a wrapper function around the functions of the R package Rstan v.2.21.7 (<https://mc-stan.org/rstan/>) to calculate the Rhat diagnostic, which assesses chain mixing and convergence, and Tail Effective Sample Sizes (tail-ESSs) and Bulk Effective Samples Sizes (bulk-ESSs), which assess sampling efficiency both around the tails of the distribution (tail-ESS, variance, and tail quantiles) and the ‘bulk’ of the distribution (bulk-ESS, efficiency of mean and median estimates). The results of our MCMC diagnostics are reported in Table S4. Convergence plots were also used to qualitatively assess chain convergence (see Fig. S2). All summary statistics and plots can be found in our FigShare repository, but also in our GitHub repository where detailed explanations are given for each of the steps of our workflow.

RESULTS

Tree topology

We used the topology inferred when analysing ‘Matrix 1’ (with UCEs) and ‘Matrix 2’ (without UCEs) to infer the corresponding phylogenies (matrices available in our FigShare repository). In the tree inferred from ‘Matrix 1’, Pantopoda is monophyletic with maximum support [i.e. bootstrap percentage (BP) = 100], and this is also the case for superfamilies Ammotheoidea and Nymphonoidea; families Austrodecidae, Colossendeidae, Endeidae, Pallenopsidae, Phoxichilidiidae, Pycnogonidae, and Rynchothoracidae; and subfamilies Colossendeinae and Hedgpethiinae. Superfamilies Colossendeoidea (BP = 98) and Phoxichilidioidea (BP = 97), families Ammotheidae (BP = 96) and Ascorhynchidae (BP = 97), and subfamily Ammotheinae (BP = 99) are also recovered as monophyletic. Within Colossendeoidea, Rynchothoracidae and Pycnogonidae are

grouped together (BP = 100). The tree topology inferred from ‘Matrix 1’ also supports the following clades: Ammotheoidea + Phoxichilidioidea (BP = 100); Ammotheoidea + Phoxichilidioidea + Ascorhynchidae (BP = 99); Ammotheoidea + Colossendeoidea + Phoxichilidioidea + Ascorhynchidae (BP = 91); and Ammotheoidea + Colossendeoidea + Phoxichilidioidea + Ascorhynchidae + Austrodecidae (BP = 69). Families Nymphonoidea and Callipallenidae are recovered reciprocally paraphyletic with maximum support.

Analyses based on ‘Matrix 2’ also recover the following: the monophyly of Pantopoda with maximal support; superfamilies Ammotheoidea (BP = 87), Colossendeoidea (BP = 84), Nymphonoidea (BP = 97), and Phoxichilidioidea (BP = 91); families Ammotheidae (BP = 85), Ascorhynchidae (BP = 92), and Endeidae (BP = 97); subfamily Ammotheinae (BP = 89); and the paraphyly of families Nymphonoidea and Callipallenidae (BP = 100). In contrast to trees inferred from ‘Matrix 1’, Rynchothoracidae is not recovered as a sister clade to Pycnogonidae (BP = 71).

Timetree inference

We used five fossils to provide hard minimum and soft maximum constraints to the nodes of Euarthropoda, Chelicerata, Colossendeidae, Phoxichilidioidea, and Ascorhynchidae. Fossils were selected according to best practice recommendations (Parham *et al.* 2012) using recent reviews (Wolfe *et al.* 2016, Sabroux *et al.* 2019a, 2023b), and are listed in Table 1.

Euarthropoda and Chelicerata minimum ages were set following Wolfe *et al.* (2016). Specifically, the Early Cambrian *Yicaris dianensis*, from the Yu’anshan Formation at Xiaotan section, Yongshan, Yunnan Province, China, was used as a calibration point for crown-group Euarthropoda (Edgecombe 2010, Legg *et al.* 2013, Oakley *et al.* 2013, Wolfe and Hegna 2014), and the Middle Cambrian *Wisangocaris barbarahardya*, from the Emu Bay Shale on Kangaroo Island, South Australia, was used as a calibration point for crown-group Chelicerata (Jago *et al.* 2016).

Colossendeidae and Phoxichilidioidea minimal ages were set based on the Middle Jurassic species *C. boissinensis* and *Palaeoendeis elmii* respectively, following the recommendations of Sabroux *et al.* (2023b). We set the Ascorhynchidae minimum age based on the Late Jurassic fossil *?E. golem* according to Sabroux *et al.* (2019). Given that the placement of this species within the genus *Eurycyde* is disputed, we performed two analyses: one with and one without the calibration point for Ascorhynchidae. The analyses generated overlapping results (see Supporting Information Table S5), and so the results discussed below focus on the divergence times estimated when using ‘Matrix 1’ and all the fossil calibrations (i.e. columns referring to label ‘supal’ in Table S5).

Analyses under the GBM relaxed-clock model (Fig. 2) estimated the age of the crown group of Pycnogonida (=Pantopoda) as Middle Palaeozoic, a Siluro-Devonian interval spanning the Telychian to the Famennian [95% confidence interval (CI) 435–367 Mya]. Colossendeoidea is estimated to have diverged between the Middle Devonian (Eifelian) and the late Carboniferous (Bashkirian) (95% CI 390–318 Mya), Phoxichilidioidea and Ammotheoidea between the Late Devonian (Famennian)

and the early Permian (Asselian) (95% CI 365–295 Mya), and Pycnogonidae and Rhynchothoracidae in the middle Carboniferous (Viséan) to early Permian (Anisian) (95% CI 335–246 Mya). Our results suggest that Nymphonoidea diversified between the middle Carboniferous (Viséan) and the late Permian (Wuchiapingian) (95% CI 336–257 Mya), Austrodecidae between the middle Carboniferous (Viséan) and Late Triassic (Norian) (95% CI 340–223 Mya), Pycnogonidae between the Middle Triassic (Ladinian) and the Late Jurassic (Kimmeridgian) (95% CI 238–154 Mya), Colossendeidae between the late Carboniferous (Bashkirian) and the Middle Triassic (Anisian) (95% CI 320–242 Mya), and Ascorhynchidae between the Late Devonian (Frasnian) and late Carboniferous (Kasimovian) (95% CI 378–307 Mya). Ammotheidae diversified between the late Carboniferous (Bashkirian) and the late Permian (Changhsingian) (95% CI 318–252 Mya), followed by Phoxichilidiidae between the late Carboniferous (Gzhelian) and the Late Triassic (Carnian) (95% CI 301–230 Mya), Pallenopsidae between the late Permian (Capitanian) and the Early Jurassic (Pliensbachian) (95% CI 261–189 Mya), and Endeidae between the late Permian (Changhsingian) and the Middle Jurassic (Bathonian) (95% CI 252–168 Mya). Colossendeidae and Hedgpeithiinae diverged between the middle Carboniferous (Bashkirian) and the Middle Triassic (Anisian) (95% CI 320–242 Mya).

Analyses under the ILN relaxed-clock model result in an older time estimate for the origin and diversification of crown Pycnogonida compared to the timetree estimated under GBM (see [Supporting Information Table S5](#), also available in our FigShare and GitHub repositories), with Pantopoda originating between the Tremadocian (Early Ordovician) and the Emsian (Early Devonian; 95% CI 479–404 Mya), Colossendeidae diverging between the Přídolí (late Silurian) and the Viséan (Mississippian, early Carboniferous; 95% CI 420–332 Mya), and Phoxichilidiidae and Ammotheidae diverging between the Emsian and the Serpukhovian (Mississippian, early Carboniferous; 95% CI 405–330 Mya).

Plots showing the marginal densities against the calibration densities obtained when running MCMCtree without data for the calibrated nodes [i.e. Arthropoda, Chelicerata, Colossendeidae, Phoxichilidiidae, and Ascorhynchidae (when constrained)] are shown in [Fig. 3](#). There are no significant variations in the divergence time estimates between the main and the additional analysis excluding *?E. golem* as calibration (see [Supporting Information Table S5](#)).

The inclusion of UCEs in the dataset results in much wider high-posterior density intervals, and thus reduces the precision with which divergence times are estimated ([Supporting Information Table S3](#)).

DISCUSSION

Origin and diversification of pycnogonids

Our results suggest the existence of a long branch at the base of Pantopoda: the origin of total-group Pycnogonida (Cambrian, 539–510 Mya) precedes the diversification age for Pantopoda (early Silurian to Early Devonian, 435–367 Mya) by at least 75 Myr and crown-Pantopoda precedes the first unambiguous

fossil record of the group by ~206.5 Myr ([Charbonnier et al. 2007](#), [Sabroux et al. 2023b](#)). Based on our time estimates ([Fig. 2](#)), crown-Pantopoda would have been established by the Early Devonian and should have diversified shortly after, leading to the hypothesis that they may have been present in the fossils of the Hunsrück Slate (Early Emsian, ~400 Mya). However, all the fossils from the Hunsrück Slate either conspicuously lack the synapomorphic reduction of the abdomen with loss of telson, or share autapomorphies with other species clearly lacking this Pantopoda synapomorphy, thus excluding them from the Pantopoda crown-group ([Sabroux et al. 2024](#)). The absence of known pantopods from the Hunsrück Slate might indicate that crown-pantopods were not present in the shallow-water environment that the Hunsrück Slate samples, and might have been confined to different ecological conditions to extant pantopods.

Ascorhynchidae was the earliest Pantopoda family to diversify, originating in a Late Devonian to late Carboniferous interval (378–307 Mya). Estimates of the age of ascorhynchids are consistent with the age of the fossil *?E. golem* even when *?E. golem* is not used to provide node age constraints in our fixed tree topology. The diversification of the superfamily Nymphonoidea (336–257 Mya), and families Ammotheidae (318–252 Mya), Austrodecidae (340–223 Mya), Colossendeidae (320–242 Mya), Phoxichilidiidae (301–230 Mya), Pallenopsidae (261–189 Mya), Endeidae (252–168 Mya), and lastly Pycnogonidae (238–154 Mya) then followed, spanning the Late Devonian to the Late Jurassic. The inclusion of UCEs in the dataset reduces the precision with which divergence times are estimated, with an average interval for family diversification of 80.2 Myr when the UCEs are included and of 76.3 Myr when UCEs are excluded (see [Supporting Information Table S3](#) for details). The widening of such estimated confidence intervals might be a consequence of the high rates of missing data in the UCE dataset (95.70% on average). Furthermore, the inclusion of UCEs leads to older divergence time estimates, with a mean difference of 13 Myr compared to the results inferred with ‘Matrix 2’. There is an exception to this observation: time estimates for family Pycnogonidae are older when UCEs are not included, probably reflecting alternative topologies (Rhynchothoracidae clusters with Pycnogonidae when the UCEs are included and with Austrodecidae when they are not). The divergence time estimate of Rhynchothoracidae also changes remarkably with the inclusion of UCEs (290 Mya), in contrast to when they are excluded (340 Mya). The credibility intervals also differ, being respectively 89 and 104 Myr, with a loss of precision when UCEs are excluded. Potential causes of this discrepancy are the UCE-rich terminals, the change in tree topology, or a combination of both.

Estimates for the age of lower ranking taxa are proportionally more reliable (narrower confidence intervals) given that the taxonomic sampling is both more exhaustive and more representative: when taxa are represented by a small proportion of their full diversity, their ages can be systematically underestimated ([Schulte 2013](#)). As such, including the maximum sampling of species is expected to maximize the accuracy of the earliest diversification event in a clade. Here, we included ~13% of the total Pantopoda known diversity (178 of 1400 described species) ([Supporting](#)

Figure 2. Timetree of Pycnogonida crown group (=Pantopoda) derived using Matrix 1 and the GBM relaxed-clock model. Calibrated nodes are represented with red dots.

Figure 3. Comparison of time densities estimated for each calibrated node (Arthropoda, Chelicerata, Colossendeidae, Phoxichilidoidea, Ascorhynchidae): calibration density (black, prior distribution specified based on our interpretation of the fossil record), marginal density (red, the ‘effective prior’ that MCMCtree uses when data are included, which results as part of the joint prior estimation), and posterior time densities (blue and green under the GBM and ILN relaxed-clock models, respectively; densities used to estimate the mean posterior divergence times and corresponding CIs under each clock).

Information Table S2). Most families are well sampled: Colossendeidae are represented by members of both subfamilies Hedgpethiinae and Colossendeinae, and by four out of the six constituent genera (including the most species-rich ones). Phoxichilidiidae is represented by its two most species-rich genera (*Anoplodactylus* and *Phoxichilidium*), and so are Austrodecidae (*Austrodecus* + *Pantopipetta*) and Ascorhynchidae (*Ascorhynchus* + *Eurycyde*). Both

subfamilies Ammotheinae and Achelinae are represented for Ammotheidae, but this family is more diverse than our sampling might suggest: only nine out of the 20 described genera are represented here, and for 10 of the excluded genera it has yet to be determined whether they belong to Ammotheinae, Achelinae, or a third, undetermined subfamily. The risk of underestimating the age of Ammotheidae is therefore higher than for the families previously cited.

The families Endeidae and Rhynchothoracidae are monotypic, and the families Pallenopsidae and Pycnogonidae as well as the superfamily Nymphonoidea probably include para- or polyphyletic genera. As such, a representative genus sampling does not necessarily imply a good representation of the diversity of these families. The family Endeidae is represented by seven species (36.8% of their known biodiversity), including species from the deep west Indian Ocean, shallow Indopacific, the Caribbean, the South West Atlantic, and the Southern Ocean. Consequently, it is reasonable to expect this sampling to adequately represent their total diversity, and thus provide reasonably accurate dates. Pallenopsidae (18 species, 20.2% of total known diversity) and Pycnogonidae (12 species, 14.6%) are well represented and sampled in West Indian, West Pacific, Caribbean region, and Southern Ocean (plus additional specimens from Papua New Guinea for Pallenopsidae). Nymphonoidea, however, are a highly species-rich family and, despite a relatively high number of species sampled (46), ours may be a poor representation of the group's total diversity (10.7%).

The diversification time of Pantopoda and discrepancies with the fossil record

According to our main analysis based on Matrix 1 and including all the fossil calibrations, our estimated evolutionary timescale for Pycnogonida agrees broadly with that of [Ballesteros et al. \(2021\)](#) except that, generally, our estimates are younger and more precise, though the 95% CIs of our estimates fall within the 95% highest posterior density (HPD) of estimates from [Ballesteros et al. \(2021\)](#). On average, the 95% CIs of our node age estimates are ~50% of those for the same nodes in [Ballesteros et al. \(2021\)](#). The exception to this pattern concerns the age of crown-Pantopoda, which we estimate to be 435–367 Mya, while [Ballesteros et al. \(2021\)](#) estimate this clade to have originated 489–423 Mya. Both molecular timescales contrast with absolute dates based solely on the fossil record (e.g. [Charbonnier et al. 2007](#), [Sabroux et al. 2019](#)), which argued for a Mesozoic diversification of pantopods based on their interpreted first appearance in the Jurassic. The long branch found in molecular phylogenies, at the base of Pycnogonida, was suggested to represent an additional argument in favour of a late diversification ([Sabroux et al. 2017](#)), but the lengths of branches in phylograms confound rate and time, and a long branch can emerge also if the rate of evolution is high. A rapid radiation at the origin of the crown-group has been further suggested to explain difficulties in resolving pantopod interfamilial relationships.

The contrast between our molecular timescale and fossil-based timescales is unsurprising; the sea spider fossil record lacks a stratigraphic structure that correlates with phylogeny and is sporadic with most of the families and superfamilies (e.g. Ammotheoidea, Nymphonoidea) totally unrepresented. Our results are notably consistent with previous molecular timescales ([Ballesteros et al. 2021](#)), despite some differences, such as slightly younger estimates and smaller credibility intervals. This is particularly interesting given that our dataset encompasses a much broader taxon sampling of in-group (198 vs 89) taxa, as well as an extensively revised set of calibrations formulated following best practice principles ([Parham et al. 2012](#)) and reflecting an updated taxonomy.

Unlike [Ballesteros et al. \(2021\)](#), our study did not use Silurian *H. dasos* as a calibration for crown-Pantopoda, Jurassic

Palaeopycnogonides gracilis was not used to constrain the minimum age of crown-Ammonotheidae, Jurassic ?*E. golem* was used to constrain the age of crown-Ascorhynchidae ([Sabroux et al. 2019, 2023b](#), [Siveter et al. 2023](#)), and we used a different set of calibrations outside Pycnogonida (i.e. Euarthropoda age constrained with *Y. dianensis* and Chelicerata with *W. barbarahardyae*; [Wolfe et al. 2016](#)).

The most significant difference between our results and those of [Ballesteros et al. \(2021\)](#) concerns the inferred age of crown-Pantopoda, which is perhaps the only node for which our estimates fail to fall fully within the 95% HPD for the same node inferred in their study. Nevertheless, the two estimates do overlap substantially. This difference results from the reinterpretation of the Silurian *H. dasos*, which has been reclassified as a stem- rather than a crown-pantopod, based on the discovery of new morphological data ([Siveter et al. 2023](#)) after the study of [Ballesteros et al. \(2021\)](#). This change leads naturally to our younger estimate for the age of crown-Pantopoda, as [Ballesteros et al. \(2021\)](#) found when they excluded the calibration based on *H. dasos*. The broad similarity in the remaining clade age estimates from these studies could be explained in terms of the informativeness of the molecular data, which makes the clade age estimates largely robust to changes in node age constraints within crown-Pantopoda. Alternatively, clade age similarity may instead reflect the relative uninformative nature of the calibrations within crown-Pantopoda since, for both molecular timescales, the fossil minima are a poor approximation of clade ages. These competing interpretations are not mutually exclusive and the reason for the similarity between molecular timescales is probably a combination of both the strength of the temporal signal in the molecular data and the weakness of the calibrations, which are few in number and imprecise.

These insights are informative of how progress may be made in refining the timescale of pycnogonid evolution since the volume of molecular sequence data has already outstripped the informativeness of the calibrations. Rather, greater accuracy and precision are most likely to be utilized through improvements in the number and nature of calibrations. The existing fossil record has recently been reviewed and revised ([Siveter et al. 2023](#); [Sabroux et al. 2023b, 2024](#)), and so it is unlikely that further insights lie in that direction. However, our molecular timescale predicts the time intervals most likely to yield new discoveries through prospecting ecologically appropriate Fossil-Lagerstätten. Alternatively, it may be possible to utilize greater insight from the fossil record through combined phylogenetic analyses of molecular and morphological data in which branch length information is obtained not only from the molecular data from living species, but also from the morphological similarities and differences between both the living and fossil species. The greatest impediment to this next logical step probably lies with the paucity of anatomical information available for fossil species, of which the internal anatomy is mostly unknown.

CONCLUSION

We recover the divergence of pycnogonids from the rest of the chelicerates during the Cambrian (539–510 Mya). The pycnogonid crown-group (=Pantopoda) diversified ~100 Myr later in an interval spanning the early Silurian to Late Devonian (435–367 Mya), preceding the appearance of the first pantopod

fossil by ~206.5 Myr. The estimated appearance dates of pantopod families between the Late Devonian and the Late Jurassic (378–154 Mya, time span between Pycnogonidae and Ascorhynchidae time estimates) also create significant ghost lineages. Despite this mismatch with hypothesized evolutionary trajectories suggested from the fossil record alone, our estimates support previous divergence time estimations that suggested more ancient diversification for sea spiders. With continued efforts to enhance the sampling of living sea spiders and the discovery of new fossil specimens, we are on the brink of refining these time estimates, leading to a deeper and more accurate understanding of their evolutionary history.

SUPPLEMENTARY DATA

Supplementary data are available at *Evolutionary Journal of the Linnean Society* online.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data, scripts, tables, and figures generated throughout this study are available in our FigShare repository (<https://figshare.com/s/f41a2898b504bd080e9c>). In addition, a step-by-step tutorial for users to reproduce all our timetree inference analyses is available in our GitHub repository (<https://github.com/morenavana/cspiders-divtimes>).

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